

Porous Silk Fibroin Scaffolds Prepared by Formic and Phosphoric Acid Dissolution Method

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Abstract

The increased need for organ and tissue transplantation have increased the demand for biomaterials applications. Silk fibroin (SF) is a biopolymer obtained from the silkworm species *Bombyx Mori*. SF based scaffolds are biocompatible, biodegradable, have low immunogenicity, and have excellent mechanical properties. Since SF is a complex protein and 75% of its amino acids are hydrophobic and non-polar, there are few solvents available that can fully solve fibroin. However, the solvation of SF is the first step in biomaterial applications and it is crucial since solvation step can alter final scaffold properties. In literature, strong ionic salts are used for the dissolution of SF. However, strong ionic salts provide a harsh environment resulting in the disruption of the hierarchical structure, and thus degradation of SF. The preservation of the structure of SF at the nanoscale enables better mechanical properties in SF scaffolds. Research showed that formic acid, an organic acid solvent, enabled conservation of the hierarchical structure of SF while dissolving it. In this study, SF was dissolved in various formic acid – phosphoric acid concentrations for different durations to alter its molecular weight and secondary structure. Then, the effect of freezing rate on the porous structure was investigated. Simultaneously, SF solutions were obtained using conventional lithium bromide dissolution technique and the results were compared.

Keywords: tissue engineering, silk fibroin, scaffold, porous

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1. Introduction

The need for organ transplantation is increasing each year and available organ donors fail to meet the demands [1]. For this reason, there is an increasing interest towards tissue engineering and regeneration of organs [2]. The use of biocompatible materials is an essential part of this approach. Tissue scaffolds typically contain tissue – specific cells or biological factors that induces regeneration of the targeted tissue by providing a three dimensional space which further enables

proliferation and differentiation of cells [2]. An ideal scaffold should be biocompatible, and biodegradable, anti – inflammatory, anti – immunogenic, and able to meet the tissue specific mechanical requirements [3].

Silk Fibroin (SF), a protein that is obtained from the cocoons of the silk worm (*Bombyx Mori*), inherently has tailorable properties to match with the desired tissue for obtaining an ideal scaffold [4]. Natural SF have superior mechanical properties including a fracture strain of 4% - 26%, strength between 300 – 740 MPa,

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and a toughness of 70 – 80 MJ/m³, which is even higher than the toughness of Kevlar (50 MJ/m³) [5].

SF can be dissolved in a variety of organic and inorganic solvents and it can be processed to be used in different forms for different biomedical applications [4]. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of SF can be tailored depending on the tissue of interest, which allows adjustment of its elastic modulus and strength to mimic the targeted tissue [6]. In addition, the degradation characteristics of SF can be controlled by process parameters, such as production method and crystal structure, to obtain desired degradation kinetics in the human body [4]. SF scaffolds are fabricated in various forms, including fiber, sponge, film, and hydrogel, to be used in delivery of healthy cells to damaged tissue and facilitate regeneration [7]. For instance, in one study where porous SF scaffolds were used for the regeneration of the cardiac tissue, only a mild immune response was observed upon the implantation of SF scaffold and the fibrous tissue was shown to disappear after eight weeks in vivo [6].

The first step in the production of SF scaffold is the dissolution of the protein in a suitable solvent. Silk fibers obtained from *Bombyx mori*, contain a light chain (~26 kDa) and a heavy chain (~390 kDa) connected by disulfide bonds [4]. The secondary structure of SF consists of α -helix (Silk I) and β – sheet (Silk II) [4]. This structure is enveloped by sericin protein, whose separation from fibroin requires an alkaline environment [8]. The 75 % of amino acids that make up the structure of SF are nonpolar and hydrophobic, which makes SF hard to dissolve in most solvents [9]. Moreover, SF has high crystallinity and the high volume of hydrogen bonding in the structure is also affecting its solubility [10]. The common solvents for SF include aqueous solvents of high ionic character, organic acids, or organic acid – salt systems. CaCl₂ – Ethanol – H₂O, LiBr – H₂O, Ca(NO₃)₂ – Ethanol – H₂O, formic acid – phosphoric acid can be given as examples [9], [11], [12]. The type of solvent is also known to effect molecular weight of SF, and its properties, hence the choice of solvent is crucial in SF scaffold fabrication [9]. Generally, in SF studies, dissolution by LiBr is preferred [13] moreover LiBr dissolution can be considered as the conventional method.

Most of the aforementioned solvents cause the deterioration of the hierarchical structure of SF and lead to degradation of the molecule [14]. For this reason,

scaffolds obtained from SF solutions are weaker and more brittle compared to natural silk fibers [15]. Thus, a SF solution that is obtained without the degradation of the nanofiber structure leads to improved mechanical properties [14]. In a study conducted by Ming et al., SF was dissolved in formic acid – hydroxyapatite (HAP) system after degumming and results showed an increase in the β – sheet content of the structure [16]. Moreover, an increase in fracture strength (2.32 – 4.43 MPa) and ductility (53.27% - 67.54%) was also observed [16]. Additionally, other than the improvement of mechanical properties, the conservation of the nanofibrous structure enhances biocompatibility by promoting cellular growth [17]. Formic acid is a promising solvent for SF as it sustains the hierarchy in the nano – scale [14]. Formic acid has two outcomes working against each other when interacting with SF; it induces solvation and crystallization simultaneously [18]. While in solution with formic acid, SF is in random coil conformation and the removal of formic acid from SF triggers β – sheet formation [18].

The choice of process and process parameters for scaffold fabrication has a direct correlation with obtained properties. The fabrication parameters can be classified according to the manner they effect SF properties: i) parameters that effect molecular weight distribution, and ii) effect pore morphology and size. During the dissolution of SF, molecular weight distribution and SF properties change. In one study, SF was dissolved in LiBr aqueous solution which resulted in SF molecular weight to decrease below 100kDa [19]. Consequently, toughness of SF also decreased [19].

The ideal scaffold should provide an environment that allows for penetration of the cells and transportation of nutrients. This environment can be realized by scaffolds with high porosity and interconnected pore structure [20]. In the study of Kim et al., scaffolds prepared with aqueous solution approach to have more than 90% porosity exhibit ed compressive strength and elastic modulus values of 320±10 kPa and 3330±500 kPa, respectively [21]. Furthermore, the removal of cellular waste necessitates and interconnected porous structure [3]. Aside from pore content, pore size is another important aspect of tissue scaffolds. Cells interact with biomaterials via the ligands present on the surface of the scaffolds [3]. For an interconnected pore architecture, the decrease of pore size increases the available surface area that the cells can adhere. However, the

pores should still be large enough to provide sufficient volume for the migration of cells into the scaffold. Therefore, the pore size should be optimized for the maximum surface area, while maintaining the necessary space for cellular migration. For instance, pore size must be above 20 μm and ideally in the range of 100 – 200 μm for the migration of fibroblasts [22]. Moreover, it was shown that although for the adhesion and proliferation of cells a pore size of 100 μm is enough, for migration of cells pore size must be above 100 μm [23].

In this study, by controlling dissolution and freezing parameters during SF scaffold fabrication, we investigated an alternative approach to control scaffold properties by using Formic acid dissolution and freeze drying. To the best of our knowledge Formic Acid dissolution was not used in combination with freeze drying to make 3D scaffolds. Furthermore, comparative studies with LiBr were limited in terms of final 3D scaffold properties. To investigate the effect of pore size and morphology two different freezing temperatures (-20 °C and -80 °C) were used prior to lyophilization. The scaffolds were compared with the conventional technique of LiBr dissolution and their success were evaluated accordingly.

2. Experimental

2.1. Fabrication of Scaffolds

Cocoons of *Bombyx mori* silkworm were obtained by Kozabirlik. Cocoons were cut into small pieces (5 mm \times 30 mm) and were degummed in 0.02 M sodium carbonate solution at 80 °C for 30 minutes to extract SF and remove sericin. The extracted SF were washed three times with deionized water and left to dry overnight inside a fume hood. Afterwards, 5 g of dried SF was dissolved in various formic acid (98%, Supelco)/phosphoric acid (85%, Sigma-Aldrich) solutions with total volume of 50 mL (shown in Table 1) up to 24 hours at 40 °C or 60 °C to find the optimal solvent. Then, the experiments were continued with 69% formic acid – 20 % phosphoric acid solution. To keep the dissolution time and temperature same as LiBr method as the chain length of SF is a strong function of dissolution time and temperature 4 hours and 60 °C [24] were selected, respectively. Then, the sample was dialyzed against distilled water for 6 hours. The obtained solution was centrifuged for 20 minutes at 8000 rpm. Then, the solution was cast into polystyrene plates and was frozen at -20 °C or -80 °C for 24 hours. The

frozen solution was lyophilized at 0.15 mbar pressure for 24 hours [26]. To induce crystallization, scaffolds were soaked in 99% methanol solution for 24 hours.

2.1.2. Fabrication of Scaffolds Prepared by Dissolution with LiBr

Same extraction and drying procedure were applied, as in section 2.1. Afterwards, 5 g of SF was dissolved with 50 mL 11M LiBr solution for 4 hours at 60 °C. SF – LiBr solution was dialyzed against deionized water for three days. The obtained solution was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 20 minutes and a clear solution was collected. The obtained solution was centrifuged for 20 minutes at 8000 rpm. Then, the solution was cast into polystyrene plates and was frozen at -20 °C or -80 °C for 24 hours. The frozen solution was lyophilized at 0.15 mbar pressure for 24 hours [25]. To induce crystallization, scaffolds were soaked in 99% methanol solution for 24 hours.

2.1.3. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) Imaging

Pore size and morphology of the samples were investigated with FEI Nova NanoSEM 430. Prior to imaging, all the samples were coated with thin gold layer using Quorum SC7640.

2.1.4. Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

The β – sheet content of the scaffolds was analyzed at 4 cm⁻¹ speed for 4000 – 400 cm⁻¹ range using a Perkin Elmer 400 FTIR Spectrometer.

2.1.5. Fibroblast Viability

Fibroblast cells (L929) were incubated in DMEM (Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium) supplemented with 10% Fetal Bovine Serum (FBS) and 1% penicillin/streptomycin under standard cell culture conditions (37°C, %5 CO₂).

For sterilization, scaffolds were soaked in 70% (v/v) ethanol solution for 15 minutes, and subsequently washed with 1xPBS (Phosphate Buffer Saline). Then, scaffolds were left in 5% (v/v) penicillin/streptomycin solution for three days to sterilize all of the pores. Finally, they were thoroughly washed with 1xPBS.

Samples were seeded at a density of 20,000 cells/cm² and the metabolic activity of the cells were investigated up to 3 days in vitro using a MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide)-[4,5-di-

methylthiazole-2-yl]- 2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. In the specified time intervals, DMEM was removed and the samples were rinsed with 1xPBS and transported to fresh wells. Afterwards, 125 μ L MTT solution was added onto the samples and kept inside the incubator (37°C, %5 CO₂) for 4 hours. At the end of 4 hours, the produced formazan crystals were dissolved with 125 μ L 2- propanol. Then, optical density of the dissolved formazan solution was recorded at 560 nm using a Thermo Scientific Multiskan Go spectrophotometer. The results were normalized by the OD of samples that weren't seeded with cells.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Dissolution Behavior of SF

Degummed SF were dissolved in 50 mL of organic acid solvents with various ratios. It was shown that 98% formic acid could not dissolve SF and cause swelling of the scaffolds upon interaction. That is due to high crystallinity and molecular weight of SF, formic acid cannot dissolve SF by itself [18]. On a similar note, 85% Phosphoric acid solution caused depolymerization and degradation of the scaffold.

To achieve solvation, phosphoric acid with concentrations ranging between 15% and 85% were investigated. However, the use of phosphoric acid accelerated gelation kinetics during the dialysis stage and suppressed solution formation of SF. The acid solution has lower pH than LiBr solution, which suggested that the solution pH is closer to pKa of SF (4.51) [27]. For many proteins, pH values close to pKa of that protein causes aggregation [28]. On a similar note, SF had a tendency to form more organized structure near pKa, implying enhanced gelation [28]. Thus, the acid mixture that achieved maximum dissolution with considerably delayed gelation which was 69% Formic Acid – 20% Phosphoric Acid, was chosen as the solvent in this study. The following experiments were done by using was 69% Formic Acid – 20% Phosphoric Acid at 60 °C and 4 hours for comparison with the LiBr derived scaffolds, respectively.

3.2. Material Characterization of SF Scaffolds

As shown in Figure 1, lower freezing temperatures resulted in smaller pore sizes while higher freezing temperatures caused larger pore sizes when compared Figure 1 A-B with Figure 1 C -D. As freezing temperature of SF decreased, freezing rate and the rate of protein

Table 1. The dissolution time of SF with different acid solutions (Total volume of solvent is 50 mL)

Formic Acid (%)	Phosphoric Acid (%)	Dissolution Time (hours)	Temperature (°C)
69	26	1.5	40
69	23	3	40
69	20	3	40
69	20	4	60
69	15	24	40
62	26	24	40
-	85	3	40
98	-	Didn't dissolve	40

aggregate formation increased, which led to a more closely packed pore structure shown in Figure 1 A and D [29]. Thus, upon lyophilization smaller pore sizes could be obtained. In addition, the shape of the pores was dependent on the choice of solvent. In the study, scaffolds prepared from 69% FA - %20 PA contained more equiaxed pores compared to scaffolds derived from LiBr.

The use of formic acid as a solvent promoted β – sheet formation in SF [18]. As shown in Figure 2A, the scaffold prepared using 69% FA – 20% PA solution exhibited Zcharacteristic β – sheet peak at 1622 cm⁻¹ even without methanol treatment [30]. On the other hand, the SF scaffolds prepared using LiBr did not express this peak prior to methanol treatment. However, after 24 hours of methanol treatment, both scaffolds displayed the characteristic β – sheet peak (1620 – 1637 cm⁻¹) [30].

3.3. Fibroblast Proliferation

The viability of fibroblasts interacting with SF scaffolds were examined using MTT assay. As shown in Figure 3, the MTT results suggest that fibroblasts proliferated up to 3 days in vitro. Both the LiBr and organic acid derived SF scaffolds enhanced cellular viability compared to TCP (Tissue Culture Plate) control. SF is known to enhance cell proliferation [31] thus improved viability was to be expected. Furthermore, the porous structure of the scaffold increases the available area for cells to migrate thereby increasing viability. Moreover, 69% FA – 20% PA solution processing of SF did not have an adverse effect on fibroblast proliferation, which suggested successful removal of the solvent during dialysis.

Figure 1. A-D) SEM images of SF scaffolds dissolved in 69% FA - 20% PA and frozen at -80°C A) top view and B) side view. And frozen at -20°C . C) lower (top view) and D) higher magnification images (top view), (E and F) SF scaffolds dissolved in LiBr and frozen at E) -80°C (side view) and F) -20°C (top view).

Figure 2. FTIR Spectra of SF Scaffolds fabricated by dissolving SF in 69% FA- 20%PA solution (full line) and LiBr solution (dashed line) A) without and B) with methanol treatment, for 24 hours

Figure 3. Cellular viability up to 3 days in vitro

The increased viability of 69% FA – 20% PA solution scaffolds compared to LiBr scaffolds suggest that the organic acid processing kept the nanofibrous structure more intact. Moreover, the increased β – sheet content might have an increasing effect on cell viability.

4. Conclusion

In this study, porous SF scaffolds were prepared using an organic acid system and frozen at two different temperatures. It was shown that, SF did not have noticeable solubility in 99 % Formic Acid, however its solubility could be improved by incorporation of phosphoric acid. The use of acids as solvents lowered their pH, which increased gelation kinetics. For optimal solubility and suppressed gelation 69% FA- 20%PA solution was optimized used as solvent. Prepared scaffolds had more circular and smaller pores upon freezing at lower temperatures. Furthermore, the prepared scaffolds had higher β – sheet content compared to conventional LiBr dissolving approach. Thus, we suggest a novel dissolving technique for SF for improved scaffold preparation.

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6. References

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